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PROJECT FACTS

Funding Programme: Horizon Europe

Topic : HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-02

Duration: 36 Months | Starting from 1 December 2023

Total Funding/EU contribution: 4,995.636 €

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CONSORTIUM

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A Sustainable Ecosystem for the Innovative Resource Recovery and Complex Ore Extraction

ABOUT XTRACT

XTRACT is a 3-year Horizon Europe funded project which brings together 14 partners from 9 European countries. **XTRACT** aims to introduce innovative solutions for assessing stockpiles and tailings, alleviating resource pressure, and significantly contributing to EU Climate Neutrality Goals with substantial emission reduction. The project also focuses on low-TRL green technologies, like bioleaching and phytoremediation, tailored for mining waste piles, offering sustainable solutions for waste remediation and precious metal recovery. **XTRACT** is not just a project; it's a bold step towards a greener and more sustainable future in the mining industry.

OBJECTIVES

 Automate mineral prospecting and extraction in challenging conditions.

 Introduce "precision mining" for selective recovery of metals from low-grade minerals and mine wastes.

 Scale and deploy remote sensing for systematic monitoring of "hard-to-access" mining sites.

 Enhance an open standards-based digital repository for sustainable mining transformation.

 Evaluate mine sites and waste disposals, demonstrating the feasibility of green technological solutions.

 Organise uptake, replication, and upscaling of **XTRACT** innovations.

 Plan and facilitate the exploitation of project results.

 Communicate and disseminate scientific and technical results, fostering knowledge transfer and market development.

TECHNOLOGIES

PILOTS

